

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AMUSAT****FIRST NAME: ZAINAB****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2007 on Windows 10

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The Art of Academic Writing is one of the most essential components of any doctoral study and I am certain that this is why Euclid University deemed it fit to be the very first course to be studied amongst others. I especially find this course to be of great help because it has actually taken me back “down the memory lane” on how and what to expect as regards Graduate Academic Writing. The first thing I was particularly excited about was the video tutorial on Zotero which I have never heard about, prior to starting my study at EUCLID which I accessed at (<https://vimeo.com/231577694>). Zotero opened my eyes to the World of Referencing, I see it as an application that has made referencing much easier and more orderly because referencing can get clumsy at times, especially during compilation for bibliography. Going through the explicit course pack, I noticed that EUCLID has paved a “thorn-free path” for students as regards writing essentials which would place them a step ahead towards successfully completing the program. I believe that the standard of any academic writing can never be underrated because the interpretation of a particular write up solely depends on the quality in which it is being written. With the admonishment provided by this course, I am certain to better with my writing skills which in turn will be a plus to my career.

2) PERIOD 1 COURSEPACK

ACA-401D Coursepack for Period1 is a detailed document designed to bring students to the world of Professional Essay Writing. The beginning of the material introduces The Basics of Essay Writing (“Essay Writing: The Basics”) (EUCLID 2015,

1) giving a step by step process to writing a good essay, after which details of constructing an ideal EUCLID template paper was discussed. The opening sentence describes what a good essay aims at, which is as stated, “An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2015, 1). The material goes further to explain the structure of a good essay which includes the Introduction: it is the part that is said to be the opening of the essay, then to Body of the essay which expatiates on the main issues of the essay, before ending it with the conclusion which is the part that re-summarizes the main points stated in the body. A strict warning was placed upon Referencing, it was stated that Referencing is a MUST for all academic essays which brings us to the issue of Plagiarisms.

I noticed that in the whole of the course material, Plagiarism can be said to be the most discussed sub-topic, and this signifies how important it is while writing research work. It was explained that when writing academic papers, avoiding plagiarism is one of the most important things a writer should take note of. (EUCLID 2015, 7) This shows how important it is to give credit to the works of other authors being used in the cause of writing the research, which means to “Cite.” So basically, Citation can be used to indicate where particular information is gotten from and ample attention was drawn towards “In-Text Citation,” which means citing the author of a particular work you are using immediately after quoting them. Still, on In-text citation, there are two common methods that can be used, which are Quotations and Paraphrases. Quotations are the precise words of an author placed inside quotation marks while Paraphrases are other people’s works that are written in your own words. Above all, In-text citation is the preferred citation style for EUCLID’s response papers.

Moving forward, a certain pre-caution caught my attention where we were advised to use the first person singular as against what we were being taught in secondary school, it still baffles me, it feels unprofessional to me. More strict warnings were placed against plagiarism, signifying how unethical and unacceptable the act is. Growing up, I have always been extra confident that I knew it all concerning grammatical blunders in English Language but the aspect of positioning the apostrophe with letter “s” while indicating position absolutely “threw me off balance.” For instance, I have always had the notion that if a singular noun ends with an “s,” the apostrophe is placed outside the noun as against adding “’s” after such word. If not that seeing it in this course material means it is authentic, I would never have agreed to it, and almost immediately on Page 3 of the LIT-101 review is this sentence “ALL PUNCTUATION GOES INSIDE QUOTATION MARKS IN AMERICAN PRACTICE” (EUCLID 2015, 48). No doubt correct but putting it in use would always be of conscious efforts from me.”

Moving to Rule 10 of the LIT-101 review is the placement of articles “a” and “an” in which the latter is placed before a vowel, while the former, before a consonant in most cases. This approach has allowed me to commit enough grammatical blunder especially while speaking because I get confused most times. But a more explanatory approach that the course material provided by stating that article “a” should be put before a consonant sound and “an” before a vowel sound, has literally solved the problem.

3) STYLE GUIDES

“A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2015, 52). Grammar styles can be said to encompass many more than just correct usage of punctuations and vocabulary, like sentence lengths, use of abbreviations, spellings and so on. Also, usage of style guides depends on the kind of the writer that you are, as a freelance writer, it is not that necessary but as a creative writer, usage of proper style is of great importance.

At Euclid University, there are two major styles of academic writing preferred for usage. In this section of the material, I clearly understood that American English Style is the authorized style for works done at EUCLID. APA (American Psychological Association) is used when writing Period Response Papers, while the Chicago Manual of Style is used for Major Papers.

4) CONCLUSION

Studying this coursepack thoroughly has been of great value to me because, if not for its intense reminder and additional knowledge on the usage of English grammar styles also the “Basics of Essay Writing” brush through, I would rather have been classified as a composition writer rather than a researcher. Though as a master’s student, I have written several academic papers which were mostly termed to be a little above average, I believe that I can now do better and my work would be regarded /classified as proper academic writing. The only obvious thing that I haven’t been able to put to use is the Usage of Zotero, which I would keep working on until I get it right. Another thing I have to work on is using the US style and grammar which I was not used to before because I am a Nigerian and it is UK grammar styles that are being used in my country. Nevertheless, I would make sure to put in conscious efforts so as not to make mistakes when working on my papers at EUCLID. In all, I look forward to putting all I have studied to practice as I have done briefly in this paper.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015 *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from:
<http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed December 2019).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.